

DIP PLANE
VERTICAL ANGLE AND DIRECTION

1. G1-G16 DIP PLANE NW-SE

$D = 136.85$

Dif. Elevation = 14.21

MEMBER II

$DIP = 5^{\circ} 55' 41''$

2. G19-G16 DIP PLANE NW-SE

$D = 38.55$

Dif. Elev. 3.72

$DIP = 5^{\circ} 30' 42''$

3. G18-G16 DIP PLANE NW-SE

MEMBER II

$D = 43.55$

Dif. elev. $5^{\circ} 14' 52''$ - SLOPE
4.0

4. G7-G16 DIP PLANE NW-SE

MEMBER II

$D = 74.70$

Dif. elev. 5.43

Slope: $4^{\circ} 09' 27''$

AVERAGE OF THESE

1. 5.928137957

2. 5.111864932 $5^{\circ} 06' 08''$

3. 5.247804528

4. 4.157561444

G1-G16 Perhaps truest to Dip

Dip - Horizontal Direction Angle; from best perpendiculars to
Dip-center lines: 14.50 - $56^{\circ} 30''$

14.00 - $55^{\circ} 30'$

AVERAGE $55^{\circ} 15'$

10.50 $63^{\circ} 30'$

Point G1-G16

$45^{\circ} 30'$

→ Perhaps truest angle? ^{horiz.}

DIP OF CONTACT PLANE MEMBERS I-II
VERTICAL ANGLE AND DIRECTION

1. G2-G17

$$D = 108.55$$

Dif elevation 10.33

$$5^{\circ} 26' 10''$$

2. G20-G17

$$D = 19.95$$

Dif elev. 1.45

$$4^{\circ} 09' 25''$$

3. G4-G17

$$D = 79.80$$

Dif elev. 4.61

$$3^{\circ} 18' 25.6988''$$

4. G8-G17

$$D = 64.75$$

Dif elev. 5.3

$$4^{\circ} 40' 46''$$

1. 5.436097512

2. 4.157045141

3. 3.306269411

4. 4.679415564

4.394706907 Average

$$4^{\circ} 23' 41''$$

G2-G17 Perhaps truest to dip

Horizontal Direction; from best perpendicular to contour intervals:

$$17.00 : 68^{\circ}$$

$$13.00 : 71^{\circ} 30'$$

$$9.00 : 82^{\circ}$$

G2-G17: 46° Probably truest

MEMBER II

45 30
1 14
46 44
43 16
89 60

58 36
1 14
59 50

44 30
1 14
43 16

31 24
1 14
30 10

30 10
59 50
89 60

Average Dip 5° 06' 8"

Greatest Dip 5° 55' 41"
G1-G16

Direction Average 55° 15' W of N Grid
G1-G16 45° 30' W of N Grid

STRIKE 145° 15
STRIKE 135° 30
W of N

MEMBER I

Average Dip 4° 23' 41"

Greatest Dip 5° 26' 10"
G2-G17

Direction Average

CONTOUR LINE: 16.0 : 26° 30' W of N

19.0 : 15° W of N

13.0 : 10° 30' W of N

21.0 13° E of N

10.0 16° 30' W of N

TOTAL 55.30'

N 13° E

AVERAGE 11° 06'
97 14
86 06

G2-G17 44° W of N

70
134

12 60
1 14
14

12

178
70
180
134
46

80 08
9 52
60

15 14 60
1 14
46

180 179 20
101 06
78 54

16 30
1 14
15 16

10 30
1 14
9 16

13 1 14
14.14

78 54
1 14
79 68

10 66
1 14
68 7 52
60 8

48
43 20
1 14
42 46

20 30
1 14
25 16

80 08

47.19

42 46
47 14
69 60

MEMBER II

Average Dip $5^{\circ} 06' 08''$
 Greatest Dip $5^{\circ} 55' 46''$
 G1 - G16

DIRECTION AVERAGE

CONTOUR LINE 13.5:	$38^{\circ} 30'$	W OF N	$N 38^{\circ} 30' W$
15.0:	$33^{\circ} 30'$	W OF N	
17.0:	29°	W OF N	
19.0:	28°	W OF N	
22.0:	28°	W OF N	

AVERAGE ~~$37^{\circ} 40'$~~
 $\downarrow$
 $31^{\circ} 24'$
 $+ 90 00$

 $121^{\circ} 24'$

G1 - G16 $44^{\circ} 30'$ W OF N

 90

 $134. 30$

~~STRIKE = $31^{\circ} 24'$~~

BEARING OF GRID

$1^{\circ} 14'$

ADD TO ABOVE BEARINGS FOR TRUE N ORIENTATION

<p>N</p> $\begin{array}{r} 27^{\circ} 56' \\ 1^{\circ} 14' \\ \hline 26^{\circ} 46' \end{array}$	<p>180</p> $\begin{array}{r} 179^{\circ} 60' \\ 134^{\circ} 30' \\ \hline 45^{\circ} 30' \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{r} 179^{\circ} 56' \\ 121^{\circ} 24' \\ \hline 58^{\circ} 36' \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{r} 29.94 \\ 36 \\ 24 \\ \hline 60 \end{array}$
$\begin{array}{r} 11^{\circ} 06' \\ 1^{\circ} 14' \\ \hline \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{r} 10^{\circ} 66' \\ 1^{\circ} 14' \\ \hline 9.52 \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{r} 28^{\circ} 56' \\ 1^{\circ} 14' \\ \hline 27^{\circ} 46' \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{r} 33^{\circ} 30' \\ 1^{\circ} 14' \\ \hline 32^{\circ} 16' \end{array}$

1. G32 - G24 NE-SW

D = 251

Dif. elevation .495

Dip. $0^{\circ} 06' 46''$

2. G31 - G25 ~~SW~~ SE-NW

D = 77

Dif. Height: 12.31

Dip. $9^{\circ} 04' 58''$

Horizontal Angle $\approx 40^{\circ} 45'$ w of N GRID

$$\begin{array}{r} 40^{\circ} 45' \\ 1 \quad 14 \\ \hline 31 \end{array}$$

3. G30 - G25 SE-NW

D = 101

H = 17.095

Slope = $9^{\circ} 36' 24''$

Hor. $\angle = 32^{\circ}$ w of N Grid

$$\begin{array}{r} 30 \quad 5 \\ 31 \quad 10 \\ 1 \quad 14 \\ \hline 32 \quad 46 \end{array}$$

4. G25 - G27 SE-NW

D = 439.75

H = 22.27

Slope = $2^{\circ} 53' 56''$

Hor $\angle = 24^{\circ}$ w of N Grid

5. G25 - G26 SE-NW

D = 387

H = 21.4958

Slope = $3^{\circ} 10' 47''$

Hor $\angle = 36^{\circ}$

$$\begin{array}{r} 18 \quad 30 \\ 1 \quad 14 \\ \hline 36 \quad 44 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 24 \quad 15 \\ 1 \quad 14 \\ \hline 25 \quad 29 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 26 \quad 45 \\ 1 \quad 14 \\ \hline 59 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 45^{\circ} 30' \\ 90^{\circ} 30' \\ \hline 135^{\circ} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 55^{\circ} 15' \\ 90^{\circ} \\ \hline 145^{\circ} 15' \end{array}$$

1. Q30-Q31 2E-111

D = 221

H = 17.032
Slope = 2.33.25

2. Q31-Q32 2E-111

D = 11

H = 13.51

Slope = 1.28

Horizontal angle = 90.32 with grid

3. Q30-Q32 2E-111

D = 201

H = 17.032

Slope = 2.33.25

4. Q32-Q37 2E-111

D = 129.17

H = 22.27

Slope = 2.23.25

Horizontal angle = 54.0 with grid

5. Q32-Q35 2E-111

D = 387

H = 2.4118

Slope = 3.10.47

Horizontal angle = 2.33

6. G30 - G27 SE-NW

D = 540

H = 39.365

Slope = 4° 10' 09"

Hor < = 25° 30'

8° 30
1 14

9 44

7. G30 - G26 SE-NW

D = 488

H = 39.5948

Slope = 4° 38' 19"

Hor < = 35°

19.55

8. G33 - G22 NE-SW BED 6, TOP

3 97

D = 152.5

H = 4.175

Slope = 1° 34' 05"

Hor < = 26° 45' E of N

26° 30
1 14

27 44

9. G24 - G20 S-N

D = 578.80

H = 11.6698

Slope = 1° 09' 18"

Hor < = 10° 45' E of N Grid

10. G23 - G32 SW-NE

D = 194.5

H = 1.115

Slope = 0° 19' 42"

Hor < = 35° E of N Grid

35

11. G24 - G32 SW-NE

D = 251

H = .495 (Down NE to SW)

Slope = 0° 06' 46"

Hor < = 44° E of N Grid

304
219

85

25° 30
1 14

44

G2 - G26 SE-NW
DISTANCE - 361.5
D.f. hei : 25.2848
Slope : 4°
Hor < N 22° 30' W

G32 - G26
D = 440.5
D.f. hei = 22.8748
Slope = 2° 58' 21"
< Hz = N 24° 46' W
half dip
half bearing

G2 - G27
D : 431
D.f. hei : 26.055
Slope 3° 27' 34"
Hor < N 12° 30' W

G8 - 26
D = 400
D.f. hei : 30.3148
Slope 4° 20' 02"
Hor < N 28° 30' W

G8 - G27
D = 461.75
D.f. hei : 31.085
Slope : N 3° 51' 04" W
< Hz 18° 30'

SPHINX HEAD elevation

12

1/2

25-20
1 14
24 546